

INSTRUCTIONS: Authorized personnel are asked to complete this questionnaire when confronted with a reportable injury.

A. Event information

Date of incident: ____/____/____ DD/MM/YYYY	Q1) Time of event: <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Morning (6:01-12:00) <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Afternoon: (12:01-18:00) <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Evening: (18:01-24:00) <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Night: (00:01-06:00) <input type="checkbox"/> 88. Did not know / remember	Q2) Who brought you to the hospital? <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Self <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Mother <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Father <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Both parents <input type="checkbox"/> 5. Other family member <input type="checkbox"/> 6. Friend <input type="checkbox"/> 7. Other <input type="checkbox"/> 88. Did not know / remember	Q3) How did you arrive at the hospital? <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Taxi <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Walked <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Bicycle <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Private vehicle <input type="checkbox"/> 5. Motorbike <input type="checkbox"/> 6. Other form of transport <input type="checkbox"/> 88. Did not know / remember	Q4) How long did it take you to get to the hospital? <input type="checkbox"/> 1. 0-30 minutes <input type="checkbox"/> 2. 31-60 minutes <input type="checkbox"/> 3. 1-2 hours <input type="checkbox"/> 4. 2 hours or more <input type="checkbox"/> 88. Did not know / remember
Date reported: ____/____/____ DD/MM/YYYY				

B. Environment

Q5) Where did the incident take place?

1. At home 2. In school 3. At workplace 4. Highway / street 5. Other place
 88. Did not know / remember

C. Respondent information

Q6) Were there multiple persons injured in the incident? 1. Y 2. N 88. Did not know / remember

Q7) Sex of the injured person?

1. Male
 2. Female

Q8) Age _____

- (Check if <1 year)
 88. Did not know / remember

Q9) Did you have any vision, hearing or mobility impairment prior to the event?

1. Y 2. N

Q10) Have you reported to a hospital with an unrelated injury during the past 12-months?

1. Y 2. N
3. Did not know

Q9a) Have you consumed any alcohol within the past 6 hours?

1. Y 2. N

Q11) Years of formal schooling completed _____.

D. Activity

Q12) What were you doing when you were injured?

1. Working 2. Education 3. Sport 4. Traveling 5. Doing nothing 6. Other 88. Did not know / remember

E. Injury Information

Q13) [Ask attending physician] What type of injury does the patient have?

- | | | | |
|---|--|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Fractures (all types) | <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Sprain / dislocation | <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Lacerations (open wounds) | <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Burn / scalds (all degrees) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 5. Concussion | <input type="checkbox"/> 6. Lodged foreign body | <input type="checkbox"/> 7. Abrasions, bruises, soft tissue damage | <input type="checkbox"/> 8. Multiple injuries |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Other, visceral internal injuries | | | |

F. Anatomical site of injury

Q14) Where is the physical location of the initial injury?

- | | | | |
|----------------------------------|---------------------------------------|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Face | <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Head/neck | <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Chest / abdomen | <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Extremities |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 5. Back | <input type="checkbox"/> 6. Other | <input type="checkbox"/> 7. Multiple | |

G. External cause of injury

Q15) Injury mechanism (what directly contributed to the injury)?

- | | | | |
|---|------------------------------------|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Road traffic collision | <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Poison | <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Fall | <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Drowning / near drowning |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 5. Act of violence (including self-inflicted injuries) | <input type="checkbox"/> 6. Fire | <input type="checkbox"/> 7. Animal bite | <input type="checkbox"/> 8. Other |

H. Supervision and witnesses

Q16) Who was with you at the time of the incident?

- | | | | |
|--|------------------------------------|---|-----------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Alone | <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Friend | <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Parent / guardian | <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Other |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 88. Did not know/remember | | | |

Narrative (Use this section to clarify any of the above, make notations or to identify a death):

Q17) [Ask attending physician]: How long will patient remain in hospital under care / supervision? 1. <24 hours; 2. 24-48 hours; 3. 49-72 hours; 4. >72 hours

Q18) [Ask attending physician]: Will the injury likely result in any long-term disability (6 months or more)? 1. Y 2. N 3. Did not know

Information received by: _____ **Reported by:** _____